

Experiment: communication training | Thermometer testing

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A. Preparation tools

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|----|------------------------------------|----|-------------------------------|
| 1. | This thermometer testing form | 4. | Back-up: cell phone timer app |
| 2. | Dr Lowenstein's Stress Thermometer | 5. | Pen |
| 3. | 30 second sand timer | 6. | A room with table and chairs |

B. Personal data

Participant's first name		Tester's first name	
Participant's last name		Tester's last name	

C. Testing circumstances

Date		Time	
Extra information			

D. Thermometer reading

Step 1	Set the rear switch to TEMP °C.		
Step 2	Set mode switch to ROOM (green switch).		
Step 3	Write down the room temperature.	Ambient temperature	
Step 4	Set mode switch to BODY (green switch).		
Step 5	Invite the participant to sit down.		
Step 6	Ask the participant to gently hold the sensor between the thumb and the index finger.		
Step 7	Start the 30 second sand timer.		
Step 8	Observe which hand the participant uses:		
	Left hand		Right hand
Step 9	Wait 30 seconds and read baseline temperature.	Baseline temperature	
Step 10	Guide the participant: "Denk aan een gefrustreerde, stressvolle situatie en leef je in."		
Step 11	Start the 30 second sand timer.		
Step 12	Wait 30 seconds and read the stress temperature.	Stress temperature 1	
Step 13	Guide the participant: "Denk aan een aangename situatie en leef je in."		
Step 14	Start the 30 second sand timer.		
Step 15	Wait 30 seconds and read the stress temperature.	Stress temperature 2	
Step 16	Ask the participant to let go of the sensor.		

Thermometer specifications

As asserted by Lowenstein (2002), the

specification and the details of the Stress Thermometer are as follows:

- [1.] Unit size 2 3/4 inches long, 2 1/8 inches high, 5/8 inches wide
- [2.] LCD Digital Thermometer with Research Grade Temperature Sensor for fast, accurate readings.
- [3.] It displays stress level to the nearest 0.10 F. (e.g., 83.5F, 85.6, 90.8).
- [4.] The suggested use for Stress Management is Rehab, Employee Training, Education, Hypnosis, Psychotherapy, Counseling, & Sports and Exercise.
- [5.] A large display which is easy to read.
- [6.] 3/4 inch high contrast LCD display
- [7.] Displays temperature to the nearest 0.1.
- [8.] Thermistor wire length—10 ft.
- [9.] IN/OUT switch to monitor both body temperature and room temperature. Temperature updates every 2 seconds, Accuracy +/- 1.80 F.
- [10.] Displays Fahrenheit or Celsius Temperature. Electronic Quartz Accuracy.
- [11.] Temperature range 58 F to +158 F. Features—Digital Clock, Desktop stand that tilts and thus allows for easy reading, Battery Life approximately one year. Battery included.

BELOW 79° F	79–84° F	84–90° F	90–95° F	ABOVE 95° F
<i>HIGH</i>	<i>SLIGHT</i>	<i>MILD</i>	<i>QUIETLY</i>	<i>DEEPLY</i>
<i>TENSION</i>	<i>TENSION</i>	<i>TENSION</i>	<i>RELAXED</i>	<i>RELAXED</i>
BELOW 26° C	26–29° C	29–32° C	32–35° C	ABOVE 35° C

Figure 12. Lowenstein stress chart. From *The Lowenstein Stress Thermometer (SC911)* [Pamphlet], by T. Lowenstein, 2002. Copyright 2002 by Stress Market.com. Reproduced with permission.